

Addressing racial disparities in COVID-19 compliance: A community-driven approach using the theory of planned behavior

Florent NKOUAGA^{1*}

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¹National Association of Insurance Commissioners, Kansas City, MO, USA. E-mail: fnkouaga@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0004-9200-9471

*Correspondence

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Abstract

Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted significant racial and ethnic disparities in health outcomes and access to care. This study aims to explore the factors influencing public health compliance across different racial groups in the United States, utilizing the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as a guiding framework.

Methods: Data were drawn from the 2021 African American COVID-19 Vaccine Poll, which surveyed 12,887 adults from various racial and ethnic backgrounds between May and July 2021. A weighted Ordinary Least Squares regression analysis was employed to examine the relationship between TPB constructs—attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control—and public health compliance, controlling for demographic variables and partisanship.

Results: TPB constructs were significant predictors of compliance across all racial groups, though their influence varied. Attitudes toward COVID-19 had the strongest impact on compliance among White individuals and the weakest among Black individuals. Trust in health institutions (subjective norms) was consistently linked to higher compliance across all groups. Perceived behavioral control, particularly health access, was a significant predictor for most groups except Asian Americans. Partisanship significantly influenced compliance, especially among Black individuals and Latinos. Universal demographic predictors of compliance included being female and older age.

Conclusion: This study uncovers a complex interaction between psychological, social, and demographic factors in shaping public health compliance during the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings highlight the necessity for tailored, culturally sensitive interventions to enhance public health compliance and address racial disparities in health outcomes

Take-home message: Tailored interventions that build trust and address the unique cultural and racial experiences of communities are essential for enhancing COVID-19 public health compliance and reducing disparities in health outcomes.

Keywords: COVID-19; community-based participatory research; partisanship; public health compliance; racial health disparities; theory planned behaviors.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted racial disparities in health outcomes, with minority communities experiencing higher rates of infection, hospitalizations, and deaths [1-3]. Understanding these disparities through the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) provides valuable insights into factors influencing adherence to health guidelines. The TPB suggests that attitudes, perceived social norms, and behavioral control influence intentions to engage in health behaviors [4-6]. Research shows that experiences of racial discrimination in healthcare significantly impact these factors, resulting in lower vaccination rates and adherence to preventive measures among minority groups [2,5]. Addressing these inequities and promoting trust through culturally sensitive healthcare practices can improve adherence to COVID-19 health guidelines, reducing disparities [1,7,8]. This research highlights the importance of integrating social and behavioral sciences to develop effective, inclusive, and equitable public health strategies.

Building on existing research, exploring how racial experiences shape adherence to COVID-19 health guidelines using the TPB is crucial. While studies have shown disparities in health outcomes and vaccination rates, there is less knowledge about differences in attitudes, perceived norms, and behavioral control regarding COVID-19 preventive measures among specific racial and ethnic groups [5,6]. Understanding how historical and ongoing discrimination interacts with TPB constructs to influence health behaviors among minority communities is a significant knowledge gap [2]. Additionally, there is a need to examine how cultural factors and community-specific social norms impact intentions to follow COVID-19 guidelines across diverse populations [7,8]. Moreover, there is limited evidence on the effectiveness of TPB-based interventions tailored to address racial disparities in COVID-19 prevention behaviors [1]. Exploring utilizing TPB components to design culturally responsive public health strategies could provide valuable insights for reducing health inequities [3]. By addressing these knowledge gaps, researchers can contribute to developing more inclusive and effective approaches to promoting adherence to COVID-19 health guidelines among all racial and ethnic groups.

This study aims to understand racial differences in adherence to COVID-19 health guidelines during the specific period of the COVID-19 pandemic and the politicization of the pandemic during the 2020 U.S. presidential election. The research focuses on data collected in the United States and uses the TPB as a framework. A cross-sectional study design allows for the simultaneous comparison of variables across different racial and ethnic groups at a single point in time. This design is suitable for capturing the immediate impacts of the pandemic and the political climate on health behaviors without the biases introduced by participant attrition over time [9,10]. Additionally, the cross-sectional approach is advantageous in capturing the salience of the context, as the politicization of the pandemic during the 2020 US presidential election influenced public perceptions and behaviors in real-time [11]. Focusing on this specific timeframe, the study aims to provide actionable insights into addressing racial disparities in health behaviors through culturally responsive public health strategies. This approach ensures that the findings are relevant and timely, contributing to developing effective interventions to reduce health inequities.

The research problem addressed in this study is the racial disparities in adherence to COVID-19 health guidelines, analyzed through the lens of the TPB. This issue is significant because it directly impacts public health outcomes and the effectiveness of pandemic response strategies. The significance of this research lies in its potential to inform culturally sensitive public health interventions tailored to the unique needs of minority populations. By examining how attitudes, perceived norms, and perceived behavioral control differ across racial and ethnic groups, this study aims to identify specific barriers and facilitators to guideline adherence. Furthermore, this research addresses a critical gap in the literature by examining the intersection of racial experiences and TPB constructs. Previous studies have primarily focused on general population behaviors without adequately considering the unique challenges minority groups face. By filling this gap, the study contributes to

a more comprehensive understanding of health behavior dynamics during the pandemic. It provides a foundation for future research and policy development to achieve health equity.

Based on the TPB and existing research on COVID-19 compliance, this research proposes the following objectives and hypotheses:

Objective: To examine how attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence COVID-19 public health compliance across different racial groups in the United States.

Hypothesis I: Attitude toward COVID-19 is positively related to COVID-19 public health compliance across all racial groups, with a stronger impact among White individuals. Individuals more concerned about getting infected by COVID-19 are more likely to follow health guidelines.

Hypothesis II: Subjective norms, particularly trust in health institutions, are positively related to COVID-19 public health compliance, with a stronger impact among White individuals.

Hypothesis III: Perceived behavioral control, measured by neighborhood healthcare access, is positively related to COVID-19 public health compliance across all racial groups. Access to healthcare is a proxy for an individual's perceived ability to manage their health, including following COVID-19 guidelines. This measure reflects the resources and opportunities available to individuals, which are crucial components of perceived behavioral control as delineated by the TPB [6].

These hypotheses aim to elucidate the complex interplay between TPB constructs, racial differences, and COVID-19 compliance behaviors, providing valuable insights for developing targeted public health interventions.

Background

The history of racial health disparities in the United States stems from systemic inequities and discrimination. Since the early 19th century, there have been documented differences in health outcomes based on race. Enslaved populations, in particular, experienced significantly worse health due to inhumane living conditions and lack of medical care [12]. The post-Civil War era saw the emergence of segregated healthcare systems, further perpetuating disparities [13]. In the 20th century, there was increased awareness of racial health inequities. The Heckler Report, also known as the 1985 Report of the Secretary's Task Force on Black and Minority Health, was a landmark study documenting the extent of health disparities among racial and ethnic minorities [14]. This report sparked research and policy initiatives aimed at addressing these disparities. In recent decades, numerous studies have highlighted persistent racial differences in health attitudes, behaviors, and outcomes. African Americans, Hispanics, and Native Americans consistently experience higher rates of chronic diseases, infant mortality, and shorter life expectancies compared to their White counterparts [15,16].

These disparities are attributed to a complex interplay of socioeconomic factors, environmental conditions, and systemic barriers to healthcare access [17]. Health equity has gained prominence as a framework for addressing these disparities. Braveman [18] defines health equity as the principle that everyone should have a fair opportunity to attain their full health potential, regardless of social position or other socially determined circumstances. This approach addresses the root causes of health disparities, including social determinants of health (SDOH), such as education, income, and neighborhood conditions [17].

Recent research has focused on understanding how racial differences in health attitudes and behaviors contribute to disparities. Studies have shown that medical mistrust, cultural beliefs, and health literacy significantly influence health-seeking behaviors and treatment adherence among minority populations [19,20]. The COVID-19 pandemic has further highlighted and exacerbated existing racial health disparities, with Black, Hispanic, and Native American communities experiencing disproportionately higher rates of infection, hospitalization, and mortality [21,22]. This has renewed urgency in addressing health equity and implementing targeted interventions to reduce disparities. As health equity research evolves, there is growing recognition of the need for intersectional approaches that consider the complex interplay of race, socioeconomic status,

gender, and other social determinants in shaping health outcomes [23,24]. Additionally, there is increased emphasis on community-based participatory research and culturally tailored interventions to address health disparities [25,26] effectively.

Building on the previous discussion regarding racial health disparities and equity, research on health compliance has increasingly focused on understanding and addressing disparities in adherence to medical recommendations across different racial and ethnic groups. Studies have shown that racial minorities often encounter unique barriers to health compliance, including socioeconomic factors, cultural beliefs, and experiences of discrimination in healthcare settings [27,28].

Several theoretical frameworks have been used to comprehend health compliance behaviors. The Health Belief Model (HBM) posits that individuals' health behaviors are influenced by their perceived susceptibility to illness, perceived severity of the condition, perceived benefits of taking action, and perceived barriers to action [29]. While the HBM has been widely utilized, critics argue that it fails to account for social and environmental factors that may impact health behaviors [30].

The Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) addresses some of these limitations by emphasizing the role of self-efficacy, observational learning, and environmental influences on health behaviors [31]. SCT has been particularly useful in developing interventions to promote physical activity and reduce smoking [32]. However, its complexity can make it challenging to apply in diverse populations [33]. The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) focuses on the stages of behavior change, suggesting that individuals move through pre-contemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance stages when adopting new health behaviors [34]. While the TTM has been effective in areas such as smoking cessation, some researchers argue that its stage-based approach oversimplifies the dynamic nature of behavior change [35]. More recently, the Socio-Ecological Model (SEM) has gained prominence for its emphasis on multiple levels of influence on health behaviors, from individual to policy levels [36]. The SEM has been particularly useful in designing interventions that address broader determinants of health, such as access to healthcare and social support [37].

Despite these advancements, significant gaps remain in understanding how racial and ethnic differences influence health compliance behaviors. Most theories have been developed and tested primarily in homogeneous populations, often neglecting the unique cultural, social, and economic contexts of minority groups [38]. Future research should focus on developing and validating culturally tailored interventions that address diverse populations' specific needs and barriers in adhering to health recommendations.

Transitioning from the literature review, defining key terms and concepts used throughout this paper is essential to ensure clarity and precision. These definitions will provide a foundation for understanding the nuances of racial health disparities, public health compliance, and COVID-19 public health compliance.

Racial health disparities: Refers to the differences in health outcomes and access to healthcare services experienced by different racial and ethnic groups. These disparities are often rooted in systemic inequities, including socioeconomic status, discrimination, and unequal access to resources [18,27,39]. For instance, African Americans and Hispanics have higher rates of chronic diseases and lower life expectancies compared to their White counterparts [40].

Public health compliance: Adhering to guidelines and recommendations issued by health authorities to prevent disease and promote health includes vaccination, hand hygiene, and following quarantine measures [41]. Compliance is influenced by various factors, including trust in health institutions, perceived risk, and social norms [42].

COVID-19 public health compliance

Specifically, it refers to adherence to measures designed to curb the spread of COVID-19, such as wearing masks, social distancing, and getting vaccinated [40]. Compliance with these measures has been critical in managing the pandemic. Still, it has varied significantly across different racial and ethnic groups due to factors like medical mistrust and access to healthcare [22].

The community-based approach and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) are highly relevant for evaluating racial disparities in COVID-19 public health compliance. They address complex social and behavioral factors. The community-based approach allows researchers to directly engage with affected populations, including local knowledge and experiences in policy recommendations [43]. This is particularly important because COVID-19 has disproportionately impacted racial and ethnic minority communities. The TPB provides a theoretical framework for understanding how attitudes, social norms, and perceived behavioral control influence intentions to comply with public health measures [6]. By applying this theory to different racial and ethnic groups, researchers can identify specific barriers and facilitators to compliance, which can inform targeted interventions. This study focuses on the United States during the COVID-19 pandemic, precisely the period surrounding the 2020 presidential election. The politicization of the pandemic during this time adds a unique dimension to the research, as political affiliations may have influenced attitudes toward public health measures [11]. By examining these factors through the TPB and community engagement lens, the study aims to contribute a more nuanced understanding of racial disparities in COVID-19 outcomes and inform equitable public health strategies [5,44].

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework for this study integrates two complementary approaches: the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as an analytical framework and Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR) as a guide for policy recommendations. This combination allows for a comprehensive examination of COVID-19 public health compliance across different racial groups while ensuring that resulting interventions are culturally appropriate and community-driven.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The TPB, developed by Icek Ajzen in 1985, evolved from the Theory of Reasoned Action [45]. It posits that behavioral intentions are the strongest predictors of actual behavior, with intentions influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control [4]. The TPB has been widely applied in health behavior research, including studies on vaccine uptake, mask-wearing, and social distancing during the COVID-19 pandemic [5,6].

In this study, the TPB provides a robust framework for analyzing the factors influencing COVID-19 public health compliance:

- *Attitudes:* Hypothesis I proposes that positive attitudes toward COVID-19 prevention are associated with higher compliance. This aligns with TPB's assertion that favorable attitudes toward a behavior increase the likelihood of its performance [46]. The hypothesized stronger impact among White individuals may be due to differences in risk perception and health literacy across racial groups [47].
- *Subjective Norms:* Hypothesis II focuses on trust in health institutions as a key subjective norm. This reflects the TPB's emphasis on perceived social pressure to engage in behavior [4]. The predicted stronger effect among White individuals may stem from historical differences in trust toward healthcare systems among racial groups [48].
- *Perceived behavioral control:* Hypothesis III examines access to healthcare as a measure of perceived behavioral control. This aligns with TPB's concept that individuals' perceptions of their ability to perform behavior influence intentions and actions [46]. The proposed relationship across all racial groups acknowledges the universal importance of healthcare access in facilitating preventive behaviors [27].

Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR)

CBPR, rooted in the work of Kurt Lewin and Paulo Freire, emphasizes equitable partnerships between researchers and communities throughout the research process [25]. This approach is particularly relevant for addressing health disparities and developing culturally tailored interventions [26]. This study develops policy recommendations based on CBPR principles, which guide the process. CBPR ensures that interventions are rooted in community needs and experiences, potentially increasing their effectiveness and sustainability [49].

CBPR promotes cultural competence by involving community members and helps customize interventions to specific cultural contexts. This approach addresses potential barriers to compliance that may be unique to different racial groups [50]. CBPR can also facilitate trust-building between researchers, health institutions, and minority communities. This is particularly important for addressing the impact of historical mistrust on health behaviors [51].

In terms of theoretical contributions, this research applies the TPB framework to the context of racial disparities in COVID-19 compliance, filling a gap in the literature. Studying how TPB constructs operate across different racial groups enhances our understanding of health behavior determinants in diverse populations [52]. Additionally, integrating CBPR principles with TPB analysis represents an innovative approach to translating research findings into actionable, community-informed policies. This combination has the potential to enhance the ecological validity of TPB in public health interventions and address critiques regarding its limited consideration of cultural and contextual factors [53].

Focusing on the COVID-19 pandemic, a global health crisis that has disproportionately affected minority communities, this research offers timely insights into the application of established theories to emerging public health challenges. It contributes to the growing body of literature on health equity and provides a framework for developing targeted, culturally sensitive interventions to improve public health compliance across diverse populations.

METHODS

Data source, study sample, and design

This research investigates how compliance with COVID-19 public health measures varies among different racial groups in the United States and how it is influenced by the constructs of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)—attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

This study uses data from the 2021 African American COVID-19 Vaccine Poll (AACVP), a comprehensive survey designed to explore public health compliance and the impact of health attitudes on behavior. The African American Research Collaborative Team conducted the AACVP. It included responses from various racial and ethnic groups, such as Black, Latino, Asian American, Pacific Islander, Native American, and White populations. The survey took place between May 7 and July 7, 2021, and involved a large sample size of 12,887 adults from diverse regions across the U.S., providing a broad perspective on vaccine attitudes and uptake.

The sample for this study is highly diverse, including a wide range of racial and ethnic groups. This diversity is essential for examining how TPB constructs influence compliance with COVID-19 public health measures among different demographic groups. The large sample size of 12,887 participants ensures statistical solid power and the ability to generalize findings to the broader U.S. population. The data collection methodology used a mixed-mode approach involving phone calls and online surveys to reach a diverse demographic. This approach was designed to maximize inclusivity and response rates. Specifically, 31% of participants completed the survey via phone (including mobile and landline users), while 69% participated online. This dual-mode approach was crucial for including individuals with varying levels of technology access, thereby enhancing the representativeness and diversity of the sample.

An experienced research team carefully designed the survey to minimize non-coverage bias and ensure accurate representation of different sociodemographic groups. Several methodological safeguards were implemented:

- *Post-Stratification Weighting:* The survey data were weighted post-stratification based on race, using American Community Survey (ACS) census data. This weighting process addressed any demographic imbalances between the sample and the general population, ensuring that the findings reflect the broader U.S. demographic landscape.
- *Pre-Stratification Quotas:* To balance the randomness of interview selection with the need for adequate representation of minority groups, pre-stratification quotas were used. These quotas ensured that minority groups were adequately represented in the sample, enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings.

- *Mixed-Mode Data Collection:* By using both phone and online surveys, the study was able to reach a diverse range of participants, including those with limited internet access. This approach increased the response rate and ensured that the sample represented the technological diversity of the U.S. population.

Study variables

Dependent variables

This study focuses on public health compliance as the dependent variable, specifically examining how closely respondents adhere to COVID-19 guidelines recommended by health authorities. Key behaviors assessed include mask-wearing, social distancing, and seeking medical attention when experiencing COVID-19 symptoms. These behaviors are critical indicators of compliance and are essential for mitigating the spread of the virus [42].

Mathematical modeling of COVID-19 public health compliance measure

Let C represent the public health compliance measure, the dependent variable in this study. The compliance measure C is derived from respondents’ adherence to COVID-19 guidelines recommended by health authorities. These guidelines focus on three key behaviors:

- Wearing masks (M)
- Practicing social distancing (D)
- Seeking medical attention if COVID-19 symptoms are present (S)

Each behavior is measured on a three-point scale:

- Strong adherence (“Definitely will do this”) = 2
- Moderate adherence (“Might do this”) = 1
- Non-adherence (“No, I will not do this”) = 0

The overall compliance score C_i for respondent i is calculated as the mean of their adherence scores for each behavior:

$$C_i = \frac{M_i + D_i + S_i}{3}$$

Where:

- $M_i \in \{0,1,2\}$ (mask-wearing adherence score for respondent i)
- $D_i \in \{0,1,2\}$ (social distancing adherence score for respondent i)
- $S_i \in \{0,1,2\}$ (seeking medical attention adherence score for respondent i)

Thus, the public health compliance score C_i ranges from 0 (no adherence) to 2 (strong adherence across all behaviors).

To validate the reliability and consistency of this compliance measure, Cronbach’s alpha (α) is used. Cronbach’s alpha is a measure of internal consistency, indicating how closely related a set of items are as a group.

The formula for Cronbach’s alpha is:

$$\alpha = \frac{N}{N - 1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N \sigma_{Y_j}^2}{\sigma_X^2} \right)$$

Where:

N = number of items (in this case, 3)

$\sigma_{Y_j}^2$ = variance of item j

σ_X^2 = variance of the total score X

In this study, the scale achieves a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.81, indicating a high level of reliability. This score confirms that the public health compliance measure C effectively captures COVID-19 public health behavior.

Key Independent Variables

The key independent variables in this study, which serve as proxies for the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), are attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. These variables are fundamental components of the TPB framework [4].

- **Attitude:** Measured by the survey question "How concerned are you that you might get COVID-19?" The responses range from "Not at all concerned" (1) to "Very concerned" (4). This question effectively captures the respondent's level of concern about contracting COVID-19 and directly indicates their attitude toward the health threat. The choice of this measure aligns with previous research that suggests risk perception and concern about a health issue significantly influence preventive behaviors [5,42]. Higher levels of concern are expected to correlate with greater compliance with health guidelines because individuals who perceive a greater threat are more likely to engage in protective behaviors [54].
- **Perceived Behavioral Control:** Measured by the question, "Do you know how to get a COVID-19 vaccine in your community?" The responses range from "Yes, I definitely know how to get the vaccine" (1) to "No, I do not know how to get the vaccine" (3). This question assesses the respondent's perceived ease or difficulty in accessing the vaccine, reflecting their perceived control over engaging in preventive behavior. This operationalization is consistent with TPB's conceptualization of perceived behavioral control as the perceived ability to perform a behavior [46]. Knowledge of how to obtain a vaccine represents a crucial aspect of perceived control in COVID-19 prevention because it directly impacts an individual's ability to protect themselves from the virus [6].

Both variables are crucial for understanding the motivational factors that influence public health compliance according to TPB. They provide insights into how attitudes and perceptions of control shape behavioral intentions and, ultimately, compliance with public health measures.

Subjective Norm: Measured by trust in health institutions. Respondents are asked to rate their trust on a scale from 0 (no trust) to 10 (complete trust) for the following entities:

- The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)
- Their state's Department of Health
- The Food and Drug Administration (FDA)
- Local hospitals in their state
- Dr. Anthony Fauci

The responses are recorded in the variables Q70ra, Q70rb, Q70re, Q70rf, and Q70rs respectively.

Construction of the Trust in Health Institutions Index

The variable "Trust in Health Institutions" is created by averaging the trust ratings for the five aforementioned entities. This can be expressed mathematically as:

$$\text{Trust in Health Institutions} = \frac{Q70ra + Q70rb + Q70re + Q70rf + Q70rs}{5}$$

This approach assumes that each entity's trust rating contributes equally to the overall measure of trust in health institutions.

To assess the reliability of this composite measure, Cronbach's alpha is calculated to determine the internal consistency. A high value of Cronbach's alpha indicates that the items are consistent in measuring the same underlying construct. For this composite measure, Cronbach's alpha is found to be 0.89, indicating strong internal consistency among the five trust ratings (Q70ra, Q70rb, Q70re, Q70rf, and Q70rs).

With $\alpha = 0.89$, the trust in health institutions measure is reliable and can be confidently used in further analysis to explore vaccine hesitancy and associated behaviors.

Control variables

The study incorporates control variables, such as underlying medical conditions, partisanship, and demographic characteristics, to ensure a comprehensive analysis of public health compliance with COVID-19. Underlying medical conditions are classified as either 0 (indicating no medical condition) or 1 (indicating the presence of at least one of the following: cancer, chronic kidney disease, COPD, heart conditions, obesity, sickle cell disease, type 1 or type 2 diabetes, or pregnancy). These conditions are associated with a higher risk of severe COVID-19 outcomes, so it is important to consider them in the analysis [40]. Partisanship is another crucial control variable, with Democrats being used as the reference group. Research indicates that Democrats were more likely than Republicans and Independents to get vaccinated, highlighting the influence of political affiliation on health behaviors [55,56]. Additionally, demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, education level, income, and race, are included as control variables. These factors are known to affect health behaviors and compliance with public health guidelines [57]. By controlling for these variables, the study aims to isolate the effects of the TPB constructs on public health compliance, providing a clearer understanding of the factors driving adherence to COVID-19 guidelines.

Data analysis

To investigate the relationship between the constructs of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and compliance with COVID-19 public health measures, we employ Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression. OLS regression is a statistical method utilized to estimate the parameters in a linear regression model by minimizing the sum of the squared differences between observed and predicted values [58]. Given that the dependent variable, public health compliance, is measured as a continuous mean index, OLS regression is an appropriate approach for this analysis. The specific OLS model employed is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Compliance}_i = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Attitude}_i + \beta_2 \text{Subjective Norms}_i + \beta_3 \text{Perceived Behavioral Control}_i \\ & + \beta_4 \text{Medical Conditions}_i + \beta_5 \text{Partisanship}_i + \beta_6 \text{Gender}_i \\ & + \beta_7 \text{Age}_i + \beta_8 \text{Education}_i + \beta_9 \text{Income}_i + \beta_{10} \text{Race}_i + \epsilon_i \end{aligned}$$

Multicollinearity among the independent variables is determined using Variance Inflation Factors (VIF). VIF measures the extent to which the variance of a regression coefficient is inflated due to multicollinearity [59]. If a VIF value exceeds 10, it indicates a significant degree of multicollinearity, which can compromise the reliability of the regression coefficients [60]. In this study, all the VIF values in Table 1 are below 2.2, indicating that multicollinearity is not a concern. Specifically, VIF values below 5 suggest a moderate correlation among predictors, which is acceptable for regression analysis [59]. This ensures that the estimated coefficients are reliable, and multicollinearity does not compromise the model's explanatory power.

The VIF values obtained in this study are below 2.2, indicating that the independent variables are not highly correlated. This low level of multicollinearity confirms that the regression model is well-specified and allows for a confident

interpretation of the coefficients. The absence of significant multicollinearity ensures that the relationship between the TPB constructs and public health compliance is accurately captured, enabling robust conclusions about the factors influencing compliance behaviors.

RESULTS

The variables of the Theory of Planned Behavior (Table 2) show significant associations with public health compliance among all racial groups. Attitude toward COVID-19 has a positive relationship with compliance, with the strongest effect observed among White individuals ($\beta = 0.07, p < 0.001$) and the weakest among Black individuals ($\beta = 0.03, p < 0.01$). Subjective norms, measured as trust in health institutions, consistently showed positive associations with compliance across all groups (β ranging from 0.03 to 0.05, $p < 0.001$). Perceived behavioral control, operationalized as health access, exhibited a significant positive relationship with compliance in the full model ($\beta = 0.02, p < 0.01$) and for most racial groups, except for Asian Americans, where it was not significant.

Figure 2 corroborates these findings by showing the positive association between the theory of planned behavior measures and COVID-19 public health compliance.

Figure 1. Predicted values full model.

Partisanship plays a significant role in compliance behaviors. Democrats demonstrate higher compliance compared to Republicans in the full model ($\beta = 0.06, p < 0.01$), with particularly strong effects among Black individuals ($\beta = 0.12, p < 0.01$) and Latinos ($\beta = 0.11, p < 0.01$). Independents also exhibit higher compliance in the full model and among Latinos and White individuals. Demographic variables reveal consistent patterns across groups: females show higher compliance ($p < 0.001$ for most groups), and age is positively associated with compliance ($p < 0.001$ across all groups). Education yields mixed results, with a positive effect for Asian Americans ($\beta = 0.02, p < 0.05$) but a negative effect for Native Americans ($\beta = -0.02, p < 0.01$). In the full model, Asian Americans demonstrate significantly higher compliance than White individuals ($\beta = 0.05, p < 0.01$), while other racial groups do not differ significantly from White individuals. Unexpectedly, employment status was negatively associated with compliance for Asian Americans and Latinos ($\beta = -0.07, p < 0.01$ for both). Another surprising finding is that having preexisting conditions is negatively associated with compliance for Asian Americans and Black individuals ($\beta = -0.05, p < 0.05$ for both). These results highlight the complex interplay of factors influencing public health compliance across racial and ethnic groups.

Table 2. Public health compliance weighted OLS regression.

	Full Model	Asian Americans	Black people	Latinos	Native Americans	White people
(Intercept)	1.91*** (0.06)	2.19*** (0.07)	1.97*** (0.08)	2.09*** (0.07)	2.08*** (0.07)	1.82*** (0.09)
Theory of Planned behaviors						
Attitude toward COVID-19	0.06*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.03** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.07*** (0.01)
Subjective norm: Trust in health institution	0.05*** (0.00)	0.03*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.00)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)
Perceived behavioral control: Health access	0.02** (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.02* (0.01)	0.02** (0.01)	0.03*** (0.01)	0.02* (0.01)
Partisanship (Republicans)						
Democrats	0.06** (0.02)	0.05 (0.03)	0.12** (0.05)	0.11** (0.04)	0.03 (0.04)	0.04 (0.03)
Independents	0.08** (0.02)	0.05 (0.03)	0.07 (0.05)	0.13** (0.04)	0.03 (0.04)	0.07* (0.03)
CNN	-0.00 (0.00)	-0.01 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	-0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	-0.00 (0.01)
Female	0.11*** (0.02)	0.05** (0.02)	0.10*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.12*** (0.03)	0.12*** (0.02)
Age	0.05*** (0.001)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)	0.03*** (0.01)	0.04*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)
Education	-0.00 (0.01)	0.02* (0.01)	-0.00 (0.01)	-0.00 (0.01)	-0.02** (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)
Income	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	-0.00 (0.01)	-0.00 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)	0.02 (0.01)
Employment	-0.03 (0.02)	-0.07** (0.02)	-0.01 (0.03)	-0.07** (0.02)	-0.00 (0.03)	-0.02 (0.03)
Preexisting condition	-0.03 (0.02)	-0.05* (0.02)	-0.05* (0.02)	-0.02 (0.02)	-0.03 (0.02)	-0.02 (0.03)
Race (White people)						
Latinos	0.02 (0.02)					
Blacks	0.00 (0.02)					
Asian Americans	0.05** (0.01)					
Pacific Islander	0.03 (0.03)					
Native Americans	-0.01 (0.02)					
Deviance	1262.16	155.60	259.92	321.73	220.92	284.46
Dispersion	0.13	0.09	0.14	0.13	0.14	0.12
Num. obs.	10001	1691	1801	2412	1583	2302

Note *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study offer valuable insights into the factors influencing compliance with public health measures during the COVID-19 pandemic among different racial groups in the United States. By employing the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and incorporating a Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR) approach, the study demonstrates that TPB constructs consistently predict compliance across racial groups, though with varying degrees of influence.

Notably, the stronger impact of attitudes toward COVID-19 among White individuals suggests that public health messaging emphasizing the severity of the disease may be particularly effective for this group. In contrast, the weaker impact observed among Black individuals indicates that factors beyond personal risk perception may need to be addressed to enhance compliance within this community. This could involve addressing broader social determinants of health, such as historical and ongoing experiences of discrimination, which may influence trust in health recommendations and institutions [2,48].

The consistent association of trust in health institutions with compliance across all racial groups underscores the critical importance of building and maintaining trust in public health authorities. This finding is particularly significant in light of the historical mistrust that certain minority communities have toward the healthcare system, which has been well-documented in prior research [19, 21]. Public health strategies should, therefore, prioritize transparent communication and active community engagement to foster trust and improve compliance, especially in minority populations.

The study also reveals intriguing findings regarding perceived behavioral control, operationalized as health access, which was significant for most racial groups except Asian Americans. This exception suggests that for Asian Americans, other factors may play a more prominent role in influencing compliance behaviors. Further research is warranted to explore these factors, potentially focusing on cultural influences or specific barriers to healthcare access unique to this group [6].

Partisanship emerged as a significant determinant of compliance, particularly among Black individuals and Latinos, highlighting the role of political affiliation in shaping public health behaviors. This finding is consistent with previous studies on politicizing COVID-19 responses [11,55]. The consistent positive effects of being female and of older age on compliance across all groups suggest that these demographic factors are universal predictors of adherence to public health guidelines. These insights could inform targeted interventions aimed at younger males, who may be at higher risk of non-compliance [47].

The mixed results for education and the unexpected negative association between employment status and compliance among certain groups warrant further investigation. These findings suggest that socioeconomic factors may influence compliance in complex and context-specific ways, possibly due to varying exposure risk levels, information access, or the perceived relevance of public health guidelines [27, 57].

The higher compliance observed among Asian Americans compared to White individuals, along with the lack of significant differences among other racial groups, challenges some assumptions about racial disparities in health behaviors. This finding suggests that disparities in COVID-19 outcomes may be more strongly related to structural factors, such as healthcare access and occupational exposure, rather than individual compliance behaviors [22].

Limitations of the study

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to draw causal inferences. Longitudinal studies would be necessary to examine how compliance behaviors and the factors influencing them evolve [9]. Second, while the study used a large and diverse sample, there may still be issues of self-selection bias, particularly among respondents who chose to participate online. This could potentially skew the results if certain demographic groups were underrepresented. Additionally, the study relied on self-reported compliance measures, which may be subject to social desirability bias.

The operationalization of perceived behavioral control through health access might not fully capture the complexities of this construct across different racial and ethnic groups. Future research should consider alternative or additional measures that account for the unique challenges and barriers minority populations face.

Finally, while the study incorporates a robust set of control variables, unmeasured confounders could influence the observed relationships. For instance, the analysis did not include media consumption, local COVID-19 infection rates, and specific state or local policies but could significantly impact compliance behaviors.

Implications for policymakers

The results of this study have important implications for public health policymakers. First, the varying strengths of TPB constructs across different racial groups underscore the need for tailored public health interventions. Policymakers should consider developing targeted messaging strategies that resonate with specific communities, considering the unique cultural, social, and historical factors influencing health behaviors.

Building and maintaining trust in health institutions is critical for enhancing compliance, particularly in minority communities with a history of healthcare-related mistrust. Public health initiatives should prioritize transparency, culturally sensitive communication, and community engagement to build this trust. In this context, CBPR offers a promising approach to developing interventions that are not only effective but also culturally and contextually appropriate [25].

Given the significant role of partisanship in shaping compliance behaviors, bipartisan efforts to promote public health measures could help mitigate the politicization of health behaviors. Policymakers should strive to present health guidelines non-partisanly to reach a broader audience and reduce resistance based on political affiliation [11].

The unexpected findings, such as the negative association between preexisting conditions and compliance in certain groups, highlight areas that require further investigation. Understanding these dynamics could help policymakers design more effective interventions for at-risk populations. Additionally, efforts to address socioeconomic barriers to compliance, such as employment-related constraints, should be integrated into broader public health strategies.

This study emphasizes the importance of nuanced, culturally sensitive approaches to promoting adherence to public health measures. Policymakers should leverage these findings to develop strategies that are inclusive, equitable, and tailored to the diverse needs of the population. Future research should continue to explore the complex interplay of factors influencing compliance to inform ongoing public health efforts.

CONCLUSION

This study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing COVID-19 public health compliance among different racial groups in the United States. Utilizing the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and incorporating Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR) principles, we have identified nuanced differences in compliance behaviors that can inform more effective and equitable public health strategies. The consistent predictive power of TPB constructs across all racial groups reaffirms the theory's relevance in understanding COVID-19-related behaviors. However, the varying strengths of these relationships across different communities underscore the need for tailored interventions.

For instance, public health messaging that emphasizes the severity of COVID-19 appears to be particularly effective for White individuals, while for Black individuals, other factors beyond personal risk perception—such as addressing historical and ongoing discrimination—may be more critical to improving compliance. The universal significance of trust in health institutions highlights the vital role of building and maintaining trust across all communities, particularly among minority groups with a history of healthcare-related mistrust.

Public health initiatives must, therefore, prioritize transparent communication and active community engagement to foster trust and enhance compliance. The study also uncovered unexpected findings, such as the negative association between preexisting conditions and compliance in certain groups, which calls for further investigation. Additionally, the significant

impact of partisanship, particularly among Black individuals and Latinos, suggests that political affiliation plays a crucial role in shaping health behaviors. This finding emphasizes the importance of bipartisan approaches to public health messaging to reach and resonate with a broader audience.

Integrating CBPR principles offers a promising avenue for developing culturally sensitive and effective interventions. Involving community members in research and policymaking can reveal local knowledge and perspectives that traditional research methods might overlook. This collaborative approach can bridge the gap between research findings and practical implementation, ensuring that public health strategies are evidence-based, feasible, and culturally acceptable within diverse communities.

Overall, this study underscores the importance of employing nuanced and culturally sensitive approaches to promote adherence to public health measures. While the TPB framework is a valuable tool, the varying strengths of its components among different racial groups highlight the need for interventions tailored to each community's specific concerns and circumstances. Future research should explore the underlying reasons for unexpected findings, such as the negative correlation between preexisting conditions and compliance in some groups, and consider qualitative studies to understand the cultural and contextual factors that shape compliance behaviors across diverse racial groups.

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